

Studying ‘Glocal’ Color-Emotion Associations in the Pharmaceutical Industry: Mapping Universal and Local Themes

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Abstract

The strong shift towards operating in global markets has posed enormous adaptation challenges for product marketing especially with regard to universality and consistency of brand design decisions. Among others, the color-in-product design decision is also susceptible to this global-local tension. A pharmaceutical tablet manufacturer that specializes in color coating and is a supplier to leading global branded companies was interested in developing a solid validated global color preference database to enable knowledgeable brand decision-making for its customers. The following case study reports results from a global study that examined the color-brand attribute associations within the global pharmaceutical industry. In a first of its kind research effort data was collected from a multi-geography gender and age balanced sample of 2021 subjects, revealing universally consistent associations as well as local patterns that are both critical to global brand decision makers within this industry.

1. Introduction

In the past two decades, there has been a strong shift towards operating in global markets. This shift has posed new challenges for product marketing such as verifying or adjusting the universal quality of design decisions through new brand images, verbal expressions and design levers (Lindstrom, 2003). We need only look at the scandalous launch of the American best selling car Chevrolets Nova in Mexico to realize some things don't translate well from one culture to another¹. As a result, it is now common to conduct substantial multicultural testing before the launch of globally positioned products. The case presented here had a similar motivation. Let us elaborate.

ColorXi Incorporated¹ a pharmaceutical tablet manufacturer, supplying global branded companies that specialize in color coating, was interested in developing a solid global color preference database to enable knowledgeable brand decision-making for its customers. Using emerging technologies in color film coating this company transforms plain white tablets into unique branded one to allow for innovative ways of distinguish new drugs. The colored tablet is used to differentiate the brand and generate emotional engagement supportive of the drug personality. This in turn contributes to establishing brand affinity.

Given ColorXi's presence in the U.S., EMEA (Europe-Middle East-Africa), Latin America and Asia, the company asked 'what colors do people in our geographical jurisdictions prefer'. It was assumed that understanding cultural influences that color preferences might be subjected to would critically aid their ability to address their global customers' needs and requirements.

2. How did we get to coloring tablets? Competitive challenges of the pharmaceutical industry

Pharmaceutical companies are constantly searching for new and better ways to differentiate their products. Despite the industry's strong growth in recent years, the

¹ Pseudo-name is used to mask the identity of the actual company

competition has long been one of the most intense². IMS Health reports³ that in 2005 this global industry reached the \$602 billion mark and, that in the past five years it has added more than \$200 billion of absolute growth. While growth rates have since slowed, this continues to be a vibrant marketplace, with seven percent growth last year and five to eight percent compounded annual growth forecast through 2009. This anticipated growth trend will be driven by many factors, among which is the emergence of new markets, including China, Eastern Europe, Latin America, the global aging population, innovative new medicines, the demand for a higher quality of life and new drug development methodologies that fast-track drug introduction.

While these trends are projected to continue to grow and intensify, the industry faces a host of challenges that make competition increasingly difficult. Growth of the branded-ethical firms is moderating, as generics become a stronger market force enjoying patent expirations, and governments' cost-control efforts. Specialty and biotech products are emerging in new therapy areas and while regulatory agencies partner with pharmaceuticals to develop and approve newly introduced drug development methodologies⁴ they also intensify constraints to ensure the safety and tolerability of new medicines. While drug development becomes lengthier, more complicated, and costly, the race for the next blockbuster drug grows more fierce and challenging (Moss, 2001); IMS Health 2005 Report). Concomitantly, as competitive conditions grow so do efforts to differentiate drug offerings.

Consequently the marketing end of the pharmaceutical value chain⁵ is becoming more powerful and knowledgeable in its differentiating practices. A proven efficacious drug is no longer sufficient. Instead, firms spend as much on marketing as they do on research and development (Hurwitz & Caves, 1988), re-appropriating an unusually large

² For example, Roberts (1999) SMJ article provides a thorough review of competitive dynamics in this industry.

³ http://www.imshealth.com/vgn/images/portal/cit_40000873/62/45/77617933IMS2005AR.pdf

⁴ For the full article see <http://www.marketresearch.com/product/display.asp?productid=1213017&g=1>

⁵ Only few studies have examined the demand for branded pharmaceutical drugs [e.g. Rizzo, 1999], and even fewer have looked into the role of marketing (Berndt, Bui, Lucking-Reiley, & Urban, 1995; Azoulay, 2000). Azoulay (2000) found that marketing had more of an impact on demand than clinical research.

percentage of their revenues to promote their products. For example promotion-to-sales ratios for drugs typically range from 10 to 20 percent of sales (Leffler, 1981). Marketing budgets are structured around relationship management with both consumers and the medical community⁶, In fact, some 70 to 80 percent of industries marketing expenditures are channeled towards relationship building and maintaining (Berndt, Bui, Reiley, & Urban, 1995; Hurwitz & Caves, 1988).

Within this context brand campaigns are developed to communicate drug personality profiles to support differentiation. Such branding campaigns identify valuable attributes and devise a strategy to promote the drug's personality in a memorable manner. Brand builders often attempt to engage consumers' senses to generate a full impact (Lindstrom, 2003). Of the five senses sight is engaged when creating a desired 'brand look' to best communicate the drug's personality profile while generating maximum sensual effect. Color is often selected as a design element of the drug that engages the sight sense.

While a color strategy can target the company brand⁷ some pharmaceuticals have devised a color strategy for particular drugs which color the tablet itself (see the notable example of Pfizer's Viagra). Coloring the tablet is assumed to have differentiation advantages by providing the tablet with a memorable look, a color that enhances and support drug features, and an aid in fighting counterfeiting in this industry⁸. Still what power does color have as a design lever? How does it actually engage the consumer and consequently build brand affinity?

3. How do colored tablets make a difference?

Color design decisions present an intriguing challenge as color selection is often guided by intuition and experience rather than science. Research in the field of psychology provides indirect support to the use of color as a design lever focusing on its ability to

⁶ Note that branding in general can happen at the level of the company, the therapeutic area and the drug itself (Moss, 2001). Our discussion centers on the latter; branding of the drug.

⁷ For example the color strategy of Coca-Cola's Red, JetBlue's Blue and ING's Orange, to name few examples.

⁸ Source: http://www.fda.gov/oc/initiatives/counterfeit/report02_04.html

promote object memorizing. Foster & Jelicic (1999) assessed memory for natural objects using implicit and explicit measure. Implicit evaluation involves the unintentional retrieval of memories while explicit assessment involves the conscious recollection of a previous experience. Wichmann et al (2002) argue for the existence of two different memory systems: (a) an edge-based structural description system that identifies the object's shape and/or contour but ignores other features and (b) a more surface-based sporadic memory system, which absorb spatial, contextual, and semantic information that distinguish objects from one another.

Summarizing research in this area (for example the works of (Davidoff, 1991, 1997) Tanaka, Weiskopf, & Williams, 2001). Lloyd-Jones (2005) argues:

Color provides a perceptual input to implicit memory systems and may be represented at a perceptual level (in a structural description system) or at a semantic level, in which stored knowledge of a prototypical object color provides an associative link between a representation of an object shape and/or the object name. Thus, for some objects, stored object-color knowledge may be used in a top-down fashion to constrain identification (Lloyd-Jones, 2005, 44)

While the role of color in memory of objects enjoys only limited attention (e.g., Cave, Post, & Cobb, 1996; Mecklenbrauker, Hupbach, & Wippich, 2001), Vernon and Lloyd-Jones (2003) assessed the effects of colored objects in which color is a cue to identity. They argued that during the initial encounter with an object, color information is encoded and activates stored color representations. If tablets can be colored to trigger specific, desired representations, then color can aid in drug differentiation capitalizing on activation and re-activation of one's spatial surface-based sporadic memory and stored semantic information.

Color, as a salient differentiator, an agent of meaning, is recruited to create user experience (Hekkert, 2001) that augment and reinforce the brand attributes of the drug. For example, a cardiovascular drug in tablet-form should not only be efficacious but it should also *look* competent. Color is used to signal meaning to support this drug's potency and generate a desired patient experience: the drug powerful because it is proven

safe and efficacious and because it looks this way. The visual experience of the tablet effectively competes for the attention and memory space of end-users, while the medical community busies itself with the package insert.

The argument we constructed so far is simple and centers on the following assumptions:

- (a) The pharmaceutical industry is experiencing powerful growth as well as tremendous competition.
- (b) To effectively participate in this industry's rivalry, pharmaceuticals put tremendous effort into R&D to hopefully produce the next blockbuster drug, while also devote equal attention to marketing and branding to differentiate the drug.
- (c) Branding typically engages the senses; in the case of a drug tablet the sight sense is likely to be a natural target. The way the tablet looks should support the personality profile of the brand.
- (d) Color seems an effective design lever able of engaging the consumer's memorized associations represented by the color.

Still, this straightforward, well-substantiated argument is insensitive to the nature and scope of color influence. More specifically,, it ignores the question of universality of color associations. Are color associations similar across different contexts? Are different cultures responding similarly to various colors, conjuring up similar images and triggering the same associations? Because many drugs are positioned as global, they require brand consistency (Domzal & Unger, 1987). But colors' meanings and associations might not be consistently interpreted around the world. The study assessed what colors are preferred in various jurisdictions around the world in order to empirically validate color preference commonalities and dissimilarities as contingent on culture.

4. Research description and results

4. a. Proposition:

This inquiry was motivated by the proposition that color can be employed as a design lever to evoke emotions associated with a desired drug personality in support of the drug brand, and that such emotional associations may vary across cultures. Therefore, this study was designed to expose cultural differences in color-attribute associations across participating geographies⁹.

4. b. Background:

The tablet medicine market is structured in two tiers. The majority of tablets are produced in white non-coated application. The smaller tier covers about 20 percent of tablet medicines. These appear in colors selected to support brand personality attributes. For example, drugs claiming to be innovative -cutting edge are likely to be produced in different colors than ones positioned as reliable or calming. Yet the science behind color selection decisions is still limited. In fact color decision makers often select colors they like and that intuitively appear connected with brand attributes. Such color decisions capitalize on intuitive understanding of the geographies in which the drug is intended to be launched as well as competitive and regulatory analysis to best understand what constraints are placed on color selection when competitive offering in these geographies are regarded and regulatory color-usage restrictions are considered.

A review of color preference literature¹⁰ including works that date back to the 19th century, showed a field of inquiry that is among the oldest and better developed areas of color studies. Nonetheless, this field is highly fragmented with respect to methodologies used [rank-order, pair-comparison etc], number of colors studied [including value and saturation], sample size and nature [single digit to hundreds of children, adults, and mixed age groups] and heterogeneity of cultures studied [usually 2-3 and not more than 7

⁹ This study used geographies as proxy to cultures (See specific geographies listed in Table 1 below)

¹⁰ See for example the works of Jastrow, 1937; Guilford, 1934; Cho & Chen, 1935; Birren, 1952; Harbin & Williams, 1966; Gotz & Gotz, 1975; Coffield & Buckalew, 1988.

cultures]. For the most part these studies could not advise us how to form a global color strategy sensitive to local association and meaning differences.

4. c. Study design:

Addressing the research question several methodology choices were made to determine the independent variable ‘colors’ and ‘attributes’, and the dependent variable ‘geography’.

4. c. 1. Color:

Previous research on color preference reviewed a small number of primary colors: red, blue, green and yellow (see Fernberger, 1914; Garth & Porter, 1931; Jacobs & Sues, 1975; Jastrow, 1937; Kwallek, Lewis, & Robbins, 1988) and some have also offered conclusions regarding the importance of color value (i.e. lightness or darkness of the hue). Still focusing only on primary colors would have substantially limited the generalizability of our findings as drug personalities vary and require a greater variety of colors to select from. Therefore, we included primary, secondary and tertiary colors in the palette with values ranging from light to medium to dark.

4. c. 2. Attributes:

Through a literature review and an expert panel, we identified twenty-two relevant drug personalities and emotional attributes.

4. c. 3. Cultures:

Eleven key markets were selected to participate in this study. Company expert panels determined market selection.

Table 1 below presents the methodology choices made:

<p>Colors Selected</p>	
<p>Attributes Selected</p>	<p>Innovative; New; Plain; First in Class; Common; Dependable; Powerful; Natural; Energizing; Safe; Fast Acting; Calming; Relieving; Trusted; Exciting; Expensive; Unhealthy; Confidence; Discomfort; Caution; Failure; Quality; Happy; Love; Interest; Disgust; Fear</p>
<p>Geographies Selected</p>	<p>US – Canada; United Kingdom; France; Germany; Spain; Italy; China; India; Japan; Korea; Brazil</p>
<p>Sample Characteristics</p>	<p>n = 2021 [with average of 160 subjects per country]; Females – 1033 (50.588%); Males – 988 (49.412%)</p>

Table 1: Methodological Choices Studying Brand-Design Relationship

4. d. Data collection:

Data was collected using an on-line survey developed and validated by the researchers. To ensure the consistency and integrity of data collection the survey was administered by a global data collection.

4. f. Findings:

Our findings confirm that specific color choices are strongly associated with specific drug personality attributes, supporting the meaning attached to drug brands (Appendix A). Still, the meanings of colors and color-attribute associations are rarely universal. In fact, we found that geography provided the most relevant level of analysis. Countries varied

from one another in color-attribute associations. While some commonalities exist across countries, each country has a strong color-attribute vocabulary (Appendix B).

Furthermore, when consistency across countries does occur, reds black and white are used for the most part. For example an attribute like 'powerful' is associated with strong medium red (7/11 countries); 'love' with dark red (7/11 countries) 'energizing' with dark red (6/11 countries), 'fast acting' with medium red (6/11 countries), 'plain' with white (8/11 countries), 'common' with white (8/11 countries) 'dependable' with white (8/11 countries), 'discomfort' with black (6/11 countries), 'fear' with black (6/11 countries), 'unhealthy' with black (9/11 countries); 'disgust' with black (6/11 countries) and 'failure' with black (6/11 countries).

Finally, while color preferences measured by color-attribute associations varied across jurisdictions, it seemed possible to group countries based on their preferred color palettes (See Appendix D).

5. Conclusions and future directions:

Our study shows clear consistent associations of colors and brand attributes that are often contextual and contingent on geography as proxy for culture. Geographical color-attribute sensitivity is particularly meaningful for brands that position themselves as global. While consistency should be central to global brands, contextual color-attribute associations suggest that color selection decisions might need to be geography-dependent and acknowledge local cultural preferences.

Similarly it is important to recognize those attributes and colors that enjoy a high degree of universality. For example, light purple is largely 'not associated' with positive attributes across all geographies and gray is universally viewed as least associated with positive attributes. Similarly Black is typically associated with attributes like discomfort, unhealthy and failure across most of the studied countries. While the effect of geography

is clearly felt throughout the data, additional research is required to better understand how universal themes are different from contextual geography-sensitive ones.

Furthermore, the use of geography as a proxy for culture was a methodological compromise that may not have revealed cultural nuances and intricacies. We cannot, for example, assume that the 1.4 billion people of China or the 1 billion people of India are culturally homogeneous. Even smaller countries, such as Spain, show tremendous cultural diversity within its geographical boundaries that might be meaningful for color decision makers. . In order to enhance the findings' generalizability and overall usefulness, a study that acknowledges cultural heterogeneity within geographical boundaries might be necessary.

This study provides preliminary support to the proposition that color - attribute associations exist: some are universal and others more contextual and culturally-dependent. It is unclear however what accounts for differences in color-attribute associations across the geographies studies. Attributing such association differences to local cultures has an intuitive appeal however future research should continue to explore what is assumed here as 'culturally oriented color palettes' that can best support the effective introduction of global drugs and/or offerings in general in various jurisdictions around the world. Furthermore, the results of this study have a particular significance within the pharmaceutical industry given the methodology that placed specific emphasis on color-attribute associations for drugs and used tablet visuals to anchor subjects' reference point when addressing the questions. Therefore, future research should also look into the universality of the associations identified across product and industry categories to better assess the breath of impact of such color – attribute 'language' and its cross-context validity.

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ⁱ From http://www.csuchico.edu/acms/BADM_001/readings/archived/Cross-cultural%20Analysis%20of%20Websites%20Article.htm - These are the nominees for the Chevy Nova Award. This is given out in honor of the GM's fiasco in trying to market this car in Central and South America. "No Va" means, of course, in Spanish, "it doesn't go". 1. The Dairy Association's huge success with the campaign "Got Milk?" prompted them to expand advertising to Mexico. It was soon brought to their attention the Spanish translation read "Are you lactating?" 2. Coors put its slogan, "Turn It Loose," into Spanish, where it was read as "Suffer From Diarrhea." 3. Scandinavian vacuum manufacturer Electrolux used the following in an American campaign: "Nothing sucks like an Electrolux." 4. Clairol introduced the "Mist Stick," a curling iron, into Germany only to find out that "mist" is slang for manure. Not too many people had use for the "Manure Stick." 5. When Gerber started selling baby food in Africa, they used the same packaging as in the US, with the smiling baby on the label. Later they learned that in Africa, companies routinely put pictures on the labels of what's inside, since many people can't read. 6. Colgate introduced a toothpaste in France called Cue, the name of a notorious porno magazine. 7. An American T-shirt maker in Miami printed shirts for the Spanish market which promoted the Pope's visit. Instead of "I saw the Pope" (el Papa), the shirts read "I Saw the Potato" (la papa). 8. Pepsi's "Come Alive with the Pepsi Generation" translated into "Pepsi Brings Your Ancestors Back from the Grave" in Chinese. 9. The Coca-Cola name in China was first read as "Kekoukela", meaning "Bite the wax tadpole" or "female horse stuffed with wax", depending on the dialect. Coke then researched 40,000 characters to find a phonetic equivalent "kokou kole", translating into "happiness in the mouth." 10. Frank Perdue's chicken slogan, "It takes a strong man to make a tender chicken" was translated into Spanish as "it takes an aroused man to make a chicken affectionate." 11. When Parker Pen marketed a ball-point pen in Mexico, its ads were supposed to have read, "It won't leak in your pocket and embarrass you." The company thought that the word "embarazar" (to impregnate) meant to embarrass, so the ad read: "It won't leak in your pocket and make you pregnant!" 12. When American Airlines wanted to advertise its new leather first class seats

in the Mexican market, it translated its "Fly In Leather" campaign literally, which meant "Fly Naked" (vuela en cuero) in Spanish.

Appendix A - Examples of Color - Attribute Associations

NEW

	New		
	#1 overall choice	#2 overall choice	#3 overall choice
Selected #1	 2		
Selected #2	 2		
Selected #3	 2		

Was described with 8 colors by the 11 countries for first choice w/light blue 3/11 and deep purple 2/11
 Second choice had 3/11 for dark green, medium blue 2/11 and light blue 2/11.
 Overall this is a blue-green attribute with the exception of china and Japan

FAILURE

	Failure		
	#1 overall choice	#2 overall choice	#3 overall choice
Selected #1	 9		
Selected #2	 2		
Selected #3	 2		

4 colors were selected across the 11 countries with 9/11 being black.
 Second choice shows 6/11 dark orange/brown
 Third choice has 6/11 gray.

Appendix B – Examples of Country and Color Association

Example 1 - Country X:

Example 2 - Country Z:

Appendix C - Universal Consistencies and Inconsistencies in Color -Attribute Associations

	Unhealthy	Common	Love
Brazil			
China			
France			
Germany			
India			
Italy			
Japan			
Korea			
Spain			
UK			
US			

Universal consistency
of Color Attribute Association

	First in Class	Quality
Brazil		
China		
France		
Germany		
India		
Italy		
Japan		
Korea		
Spain		
UK		
US		

Universal inconsistency
of Color Attribute Association

Appendix D - Examples of Country Grouping and Color Association

PREDOMINANTLY COOL COLORS

PREDOMINANTLY WARM COLORS

Appendix E – Example of Survey Questions

General Instructions:

This color study is designed to identify color associations and preferences of medication tablets.

The study is divided into the following three sections:

- Section One: looks at color associations and preferences for medicine tablets
- Section Two: looks at how various medicine tablets' descriptors relate to each other
- Section Three: consists of demographic questions

There is no right or wrong answer to these questions. Please be thorough and honest and take as much time as you need.

Each question will use the same answer pattern; first you will be asked to select a row of colors out of three available rows to answer the question. Then you will be asked to identify your three most preferred or associated colors, followed by your three least preferred colors for a given medicine tablet. Please pay close attention to the instructions provided for each question.

Thank you for your participation.

1. To help us group the information from this survey, in which of these age groups do you belong:
 - a. 18 or under
 - b. 18 - 29
 - c. 30 – 39
 - d. 40 – 49
 - e. 50 – 59
 - f. 60 – 69
 - g. 70 – 79
 - h. 80 or older
2. Are you...?
 - a. Female
 - b. Male

Section One – Color Preferences and Associations

1. Innovative:
 - a. Select the color row that best represent the word **Innovative**
 - b. Select the most preferred color for a medicine tablet that is **innovative**.

-
- c. Select the next most preferred color for a medicine tablet that is **innovative**.
 - d. Select the third most preferred color for a medicine tablet that is **innovative**.
 - e. Now within the row select the least preferred color for a medicine tablet that is **innovative**.
 - f. Now select the next least preferred color for a medicine tablet that is **innovative**.
 - g. Now select the third least preferred color for a medicine tablet that is **innovative**.

Most: 1, 2, 3

Least: 1, 2, 3

18. Confidence

- a. Select the color row that best represent the word **Confidence**.
- b. Select the most preferred color for a medicine tablet that builds **confidence**.
- c. Select the next most preferred color for a medicine tablet that builds **confidence**.
- d. Select the third most preferred color for a medicine tablet that builds **confidence**.
- e. Now within the row select the least preferred color for a medicine tablet that builds **confidence**.
- f. Now select the next least preferred color for a medicine tablet that builds **confidence**.
- g. Now select the third least preferred color for a medicine tablet that builds **confidence**.

Most: 1, 2, 3

Least: 1, 2, 3

Section Two – Relationship between Descriptors:

Instructions: For each of the following questions please indicate how strongly each word is associated with each of the emotions that appear below:

Please answer all of the following questions.

1. A medicine tablet that is **innovative** is associated with:
2. A medicine tablet that is **New** is associated with:
3. A medicine tablet that is **Plain** is associated with:

Section Three – Demographic Information

I have a few more questions to help us classify your answers with other respondents.

1. Please indicate the highest level of education you have completed.
 - a. High school diploma
 - b. BA degree
 - c. MA degree
 - d. PhD degree
 - e. Other